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New Istanbul B1 Level Turkish Course Book for International Students in Terms of Listening Strategies

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Abstract

Language has been a means of agreement since the first humanity existed. With the diversity of languages spoken around the world, the need for societies to learn a foreign language other than their mother tongue is also increasing on a global scale. Speaking of Turkish in wide geographies and the number of immigrants coming to our country make it necessary to teach Turkish as a foreign language more systematically. In this respect, course books are one of the most used tools for language learning. In the course books that include four basic language skills, listening skill is seen as a neglected skill both in the mother tongue and in learning a foreign language, so it has been examined in different course books in various studies. In the course books, listening skills are included as before, during and after listening. In this study, New Istanbul Turkish B1 level course book listening activities were examined in terms of the distribution of listening activities before, during and after listening in accordance with the determined classification. Document analysis method, one of the qualitative research models, was used in the study. In the light of all findings, it was concluded that the distribution of pre-listening activities to unit themes was not balanced, the strategies used were repeated, certain strategies were constantly included in the while-listening activities, and post-listening activities and strategies were not included. According to the results, it was suggested to distribute listening activities to all units in a balanced way, to provide enrichment by using different strategies and to include post-listening activities in terms of the integrity of learning.

Keywords: Teaching Turkish, Listening Activities, Listening Strategies, Course Books, Listening Skill

1. Introduction

Language is the most human-specific means of communication. It is stated that 7.117 languages are spoken in the world (Explore The World's Languages, 2021). Among these languages, Turkish ranks 14th in the list of languages according to the number of languages spoken as a mother tongue worldwide. The number of speakers of Turkish as a foreign language is stated to be 220 million, including Central Asia (List of languages according to the number of languages spoken as mother tongue, 2021). In the light of all the data, it is stated that Turkish

is the fifth most spoken language in the world (5th most spoken language in the world, 2021). In this respect, teaching Turkish as a foreign language gains great importance. It has been observed that there have been large increases in the number of students coming to study abroad in Turkey in recent years. In addition to this, the number of immigrants coming to our country from Syria in Turkey as of January 2021 is 3,645,557 people (Syrians in Turkey, 2021). The efforts of the Ministry of National Education and the Ministry of Culture to teach Turkish abroad are also gaining momentum in this direction. The establishment of the Ministry of Education Foundation, cultural and educational activities of the Yunus Emre Institute, International Student Academy and Turkey Scholarships of Presidency for Turks Abroad and Related Communities have great importance in the promotion of Turkish and Turkish culture. All these situations increase the importance of teaching Turkish as a foreign language. The Ministry of Education within the borders of Turkey undertakes important duties for immigrants to learn Turkish correctly and systematically. Turkish Language Teaching, Application and Research Centers, established within universities, also constitute the higher education part of this education. In this process, the systematic teaching of Turkish under four basic language skills has gained great importance both abroad and at home. These skills are listening, speaking, reading and writing specified in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR, 2001).

Listening is one of the first skills that human beings meet before they are born. Listening is of great importance in gaining the native language of the individual compared to other skills. Güneş (2013) states that listening is a process that begins in the mother's womb. The development of listening skills in early childhood is important. Ingram (1989) states that the first grammar patterns that children have been acquired through listening. The importance of listening is seen when considering the order in which a healthy individual begins to acquire language. Listening skill is the pioneer of speaking skill; therefore, the baby is subjected to a listening test in a short time after birth. Listening takes an important place in the average human life with auditory abilities. Adler, Rosenfald, and Proctor (2001) state that the time spent communicating is 70 percent in the entire time frame, and approximately 45 percent of this rate is through listening. The importance of listening with the school life of the individual gains great importance among other skills. In this sense, it is important that the ministry adopts a sound-based approach with the new curriculum, especially in primary reading and writing education. Before proceeding with reading and writing, the child is asked to recognize and be aware of sounds. Then he/she is asked to read and write words, sentences by combining the sound. In this respect, "listening, which is one of the learning areas and forms the basis of other learning areas, has an important place in human life" (Doğan, 2017: 1). People can learn foreign languages other than their mother tongue during the average life span. Listening is of great importance in learning a foreign language, just like in the native language. Unlike the listening skill that the individual is naturally exposed to in his/her native language, acquiring a listening skill in a foreign language requires more effort. Brown (2000) states that the answers to questions such as who teaches and learns the language, what their mother tongue is, what their educational and socio-economic status are, who their parents are, what their cognitive competencies are, what their individual differences are, where the language is learned and taught, why it is learned, and most importantly, what the relationship between learner and teacher is in the language learning process are of great importance in determining the degree of this effort. Listening is one of the most common skills that an individual is exposed to in learning the target language. While the individual is learning a foreign language, whether it is in the classroom or natural environment, listening is the pioneer of other skills. When the course books written on teaching English today are examined, it is seen that listening skills are not only included as a separate section, but also listening sections are included in grammar and vocabulary teaching, which are sub-skills.

Listening is of great importance in sentence examples related to grammar, vocabulary acquisition given under the theme, vocalization of reading activities, and post-listening skills leading to writing and speaking activities that are productive skills. However, this situation is not given enough attention by educators in both mother tongue and foreign languages. Nunan (2002) states that listening is ignored by remaining behind speaking skills, but the prominence of verbal skills in the 1960s, later in the 1980s, Krashen's ideas on comprehensible input, and finally the Total Physical Response method based on these ideas of Krashen, causes listening skills to come to the fore. Harmer (2007) states that listening skills can be improved in classroom and outdoor listening with rich comprehensible input. However, the thought that listening is an innate skill is seen as the reason why this skill is not considered adequately among all skills (Wilson, 2008; Brown, 1954; Thompkins, 1998; Özbay 2002).

In teaching Turkish as a foreign language, it is essential that all skills are taught and learned effectively. In this respect, course books are one of the most useful resources for educators. Harmer (2007) states that a good course book consists of a consistent curriculum, satisfactory language control, and engaging text. In this direction, the quality and quantity of the books written to teach Turkish as a foreign language are increasing day by day. Especially *Yedi İklim*, *Yeni Hitit*, *Gazi University Tömer* and *İstanbul Turkish Teaching Sets* are seen as the most frequently used sets for the adult group. This situation is examined by researchers as a field of study. The qualitative status of the skills in the books as well as the quantitative number are also considered within the scope of listening skills. In teaching listening skills, the skills presentation strategies of the course books are as important as the strategies applied by the educators. Although many authors such as Wilson (2008), Oxford (1990), Chamot and O'mally (1990) describe strategies as deliberate behavior that enables learners to use knowledge more effectively and enrich learning, there is no consensus. In this respect, strategies are expressed by different names by different authors. In this direction, strategies are discussed under three main headings in the relevant literature. These strategies are listed as cognitive, metacognitive and affective, respectively. Wilson (2008), who made examples of what these strategies are, included the following statements.

Cognitive strategies are those that we use in order to complete an immediate task. For example, a student may find out about the topic (perhaps using information in L1) before listening, in order to predict content.

Metacognitive strategies are related to learning in general and often have long-term benefits. For example, students might choose to tune in to a BBC recording once a week as a strategy for improving their listening. Socio-affective strategies are concerned with the learners' interaction with other speakers and their attitude towards learning. For example, they may choose to rehearse a telephone conversation in L2 with another student in order to develop confidence, or reward themselves with a doughnut when they successfully complete some task in the target language. (Wilson, 2008:34).

When these general strategies are considered within the listening processes, a process-based sequence is observed. It is important that the listening sections are listed within a certain period, like other skills in published course books. This order is known as before listening, while-listening and post listening.

Pre – listening activities include both the mental and physical preparation process for the text that the learner will listen to. İnce and Boztilki (2016:164) states that “pre-listening process in modern approach is the stage where the teacher informs the learners about the content of the text they are going to listen to, or tries to motivate the students to the piece they will listen to, and explains the students about what kind of exercise they will encounter.” Rost (2013) states that pre-listening activities are a stage designed for students' preparation for listening, and they can consist of a short activity for the discourse frames, concepts or vocabulary in the text that helps students to concentrate on the listening text.

While -listening activities, on the other hand, are seen as a process that allows the text to be listened to in general and in detail, to better understand the texts and to check the predictions made before listening. Field (2009) sees the listening process as a stage where students take selective notes, evaluate the speaker's perspective in important parts of the speech, use reminder cues, and mentally identify the points that the speaker refers to. İnci and Boztilki (2016:166) state that “while-listening activities are aimed at revealing the messages by the students and improving the students' decoding skills.”

Post-listening activities include answering questions after listening, using the information learned by integrating with skills such as speaking or writing, and making evaluations of the listened text. In addition, “At this stage, students are expected to find the main idea of the text, express the text in written or oral form, and make some comments by summarizing it (İşcan ve Aydın, 2018: 440). Richards (2008) defines post-listening as a stage in which students express their opinions about the subject they listen to, examine the structures of the listening text, and analyze their speech discourse. Wilson (2008: 61) generally includes the following information about the processes of listening.

Table 1: Listening Processes

Pre-listening	1 Activate schemata: What do I know? 2 Reason: Why listen? 3 Prediction: What can I expect to hear?
While-listening	1 Monitor (1): Are my expectations met? 2 Monitor (2): Am I succeeding in the task?
Post-listening	1 Feedback: Did I fulfil the task? 2 Response: How can I respond?

In the study conducted by Kurudayıoğlu and Kiraz (2020), these processes were scanned in the sources they determined and the following results were obtained:

Pre - listening: Guessing, setting goals, preparing, activating prior knowledge, working with words, working with questions, visualizing, Identifying Type, Method and Technique, introducing, setting outlines, brainstorming.

While - listening: Taking notes, guesswork, visualization, question studies, paying attention to stresses and intonations, listening again, relating, comparing, analyzing, repeating what has been heard, working with organizing charts, establishing analogy, empathy, working with words (keywords , unknown words), determining the subject, determining the main idea, making markings, classification, sorting, title generation, solution generation, interim summary.

Post Listening: Summarizing, evaluating, question studies, inferencing, re-expressing, producing titles, discussing, establishing cause-effect relationships, self-evaluation, questioning, completion studies, comparing work with organizing tables, giving feedback, criticizing. (Kurudayıoğlu and Kiraz, 2020: 400).

Wilson (2008), who was not seen as a source in the study of Kurudayıoğlu and Kiraz (2020), explained these processes as follows:

Before Listening: Brainstorming, using images, filling in the blank, keywords, working with groups, using quotes, guessing.

While Listening: Finding the main idea, listening in detail, making inferences, making inferences, pausing and guessing, listening and guessing, transferring information, taking notes, dictating, duplicating.

Post Listening: Reflecting, Checking and summarizing, discussion, creative answers, critical responses, exchange of information, problem solving, unitary solution of the listening text, reconstruction of the listening text.

In the literature, there are studies to examine Turkish teaching course books for foreigners, but the number of course books on strategy-based analysis is few. In addition, Istanbul Turkish Teaching Set has recently been renewed and released as the New Istanbul Turkish course book. The aim of this study is to examine the listening sections in the New Istanbul Turkish Teaching Set (B1 Level) on the basis of quantitative and qualitative classification in terms of procedural listening strategies. For this purpose, the following questions were sought.

1. What are the pre-listening strategies used in listening activities?
2. What are the while- listening strategies used in listening activities?
3. What are the post-listening strategies used in listening activities?

2. Method

2.1 Research Model

In this study, document analysis method, one of the qualitative research models, was used. Bryman (2008) states that qualitative research emphasizes words rather than numbers or quantities in the analysis of data. Sandelowski (2004) identifies qualitative research as an umbrella term aiming at discovering how human beings understand, interpret the world around them. One of the qualitative research models, “Document review covers the analysis of written materials containing information about the phenomenon or events aimed to be investigated” (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013: 217). Yıldırım and Şimşek (2013) state that document analysis can be used alone or in

combination with other methods. In this respect, it can be concluded that document analysis is a method that can be used alone in this study.

2.2 Data Collection Tool

The document of this study is the New Istanbul B1 Level Turkish Course book, published by the Culture and Art Publishing House in 2020. New Istanbul Turkish Teaching Set for International Students consists of A1, A2, B1, B2, C1 levels. The teaching kit can be used both in print and digital. Listening contents can be accessed using QR reader programs.

The B1 level examined in this study consists of six units. The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (2001) defines the B1 level as the first of the independent user level. Since the B1 level of the book was not included in previous studies, this level was examined in the study. Each unit theme is divided into three sub-themes. Reading, grammar, listening, writing and speaking skills are included in each unit, respectively. When Table 2 is examined, New Istanbul B1 Level Turkish Course book consists of six units in total. Each unit is divided into three sub-themes. The number of listening skills subject to the study is eighteen. Listening parts are compatible with the unit's theme and subthemes.

Table 2: Distribution of units, subthemes and listening activities in the book

Unit Headings	Unit Sub-Theme Headings	Listening Activity Headings
Ünite 1 Yeni Bir Hayat	1A Taşınma	Taşınma Telaşı
	1B Hava Bedava Su Bedava	Ulaşım
	1C Yeni Bir Şehirde Hayat	Meryem'den Lisa'ya
Ünite 2 İş Dünyası	2A İş Hayatı	Çalışma Koşulları
	2B Başarı Öyküleri	Sıfırdan Başlamak
	2C Meslekler	İşten Çok Sıkıldım
Ünite 3 Her Şeyin Başı Sağlık	3A Can Boğazdan Gelir	Sağlıklı Yaşam İçin Spor
	3B Şifa Olsun	Çok Hastayım
	3C Ruh Sağlığı	Radyo Sağlık
Ünite 4 Eğitim Hayatı	4A Üniversite Hayatı	Alaylı mısın? Mektepli mi?
	4B Öğrenme Tarzları	Yabancı Dil Öğrenmenin Beş Yolu
	4C Eğitim Habeleri	Finlandiya Eğitim Sistemi
Ünite 5 Hayallerimiz	5A İnsan Hayalleri İle Yaşar	Keşke
	5B Son Pişmanlık Fayda Etmez	Keşkeler
	5C Şikayetlerimiz	Her Şerde Bir Hayır Vardır
Ünite 6 Bir Dünya Kültür	6A Kültürel Farklılıklar	Batıl İnançlar
	6B Hayat Tarzları	Şehirden Köye, Köyden Şehire
	6C Festivaller	Festivale Gitmek İstiyorum

2.3 Data Analysis

The data were analyzed by descriptive analysis method. Yıldırım and Şimşek (2013) state that in descriptive analysis, the data are handled according to a predetermined framework. In the study, the data were analyzed as before, during and after listening in line with the classification determined by Kurudayıoğlu and Kiraz (2020:399).

Table 3: Strategies According to Listening Stages

Pre Listening	While Listening	Post Listening
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guessing • setting goals • preparing • activating prior knowledge • working with words • working with questions • Envisioning • Identifying Type, Method and Technique • Introducing • Setting outlines • brainstorming. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taking Notes • Forecasting Studies • Visualization • Question Studies • Paying Attention to Emphasis and Intonation • Listen Again • Attribution • Comparison • Analyzing • Repeating Rest • Working with Organizational Charts • Establishing Analogy • Empathize • Working with Words (Key words, unknown words) • Making Topic Detection • Determining the Main Idea • Making Markups • Classification • Ranking • Creating a Title • Solution Generation • Making Interim Summary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Summarizing • Evaluation • Question Studies • Inference • Re-expression • Creating a Title • Discussion • Building Cause-Effect Relationships • Self-assessment • Inquiry • Completion Studies • Working with Organizational Charts • Comparison • Providing Feedback • Criticism

2.4 Validity and Credibility

The listening activities examined for the validity of the analysis of the data were analyzed by two different experts according to the use of strategies before, during and after listening. Then the experts came together and the analyzes were compared. In cases where two experts disagreed, the analysis of the data was completed by obtaining a third expert opinion.

3. Results

3.1 Listening activities in terms of pre-listening strategies

The pre-listening strategies used in the listening activities in the B1 level course book examined within the scope of the research are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Strategies used in pre-listening

Pre-Listening Strategies	Distribution of Unit Theme and Sub-Theme Contents																		F		
	1 A	1 B	1 C	2 A	2 B	2 C	3 A	3 B	3 C	4 A	4 B	4 C	5 A	5 B	5 C	6 A	6 B	6 C			
Guessing												x								1	
Setting goals																					
Preparing		x	x		x			x		x	x						x				7
Activating Prior Knowledge		x	x		x			x		x	x						x				7
Working with words		x			x			x									x				4
Working with questions			x							x	x										3
Envisioning																					
Identifying Type, Method and Technique																					
Introducing									x												1
Setting outlines																					
Brainstorming												x					x				2
Total (f)		3	3		3			4		3	5						4				25

When Table 4 was examined, the following findings were obtained regarding the strategies used before listening. When the listening activities related to the sub-themes of the first unit were examined, pre-listening strategies were included only in the first two themes. Among the pre-listening strategies, activating preliminary information, making preparations stand out as common strategies used in the first two themes.

When the listening activities related to the sub-themes of the second unit were examined, pre-listening strategies were included only in the first sub-theme. The pre-listening strategies in only the first sub-theme are similar to the first unit. These strategies are viewed as activating prior knowledge, preparing and working with words. Unlike the first unit, pre-listening strategies were not used in the second and third sub-themes of this unit.

When the listening activities related to the sub-themes of the third unit were examined, pre-listening strategies were included only in the first and third sub-themes. The pre-listening strategies in the first theme in all three themes are similar to the strategies in the previous units and sub-themes.

When the listening activities related to the sub-themes of the fourth unit were examined, pre-listening strategies were included only in the first sub-theme. Pre-listening strategies in the first theme are similar to the strategies in

the previous units and sub-themes. In the first sub-theme, two separate activities were presented before listening. In this respect, pre-listening strategies take more place in the first sub-theme compared to the previous units.

When the listening activities related to the sub-themes of the fifth unit were examined, it was seen that there were no pre-listening activities.

When the listening activities related to the sub-themes of the sixth unit were examined, pre-listening activities were included only in the first sub-theme. It was seen that pre-listening strategies were not included in the second and third sub-themes. The determined strategies were similar to those in the previous units.

When the listening activities related to the sub-themes of the sixth unit were examined, pre-listening activities were included only in the first sub-theme. It was found out that pre-listening strategies were not included in the second and third sub-themes. The determined strategies were similar to those in the previous units.

Unit sub-themes that mostly include pre-listening strategies were seen as 4A, 3A and 6A, respectively. On the other hand, pre-listening strategies were not included in 11 sub-themes. These sub-themes were seen as 1C, 2B, 2C, 3B, 4B, 4C, 5A, 5B, 5C, 6B, 6C. The distribution of pre-listening strategies is not balanced in this regard. Pre-listening strategies were included in only 7 of a total of 18 sub-themes. It was found to be 38.88% and was insufficient quantitatively.

The most used pre-listening strategies were, in order, preparation, activating pre-knowledge, and working with words. These three strategies were used 18 times.

The total number of strategies used was determined as 25. The three strategies used in question were seen as 72% of the strategies used in total. This showed that pre-listening strategies were not in a quantitatively balanced distribution.

In addition, the strategies of setting goals, envisioning, identifying type, method and technique, setting outlines were not included. Besides the unbalanced quantitative distribution, it does not appear in a qualitative distribution in pre-listening strategies.

3.2 Listening activities in terms of while - listening strategies

The while-listening strategies used in the listening activities in the B1 level course book examined within the scope of the research are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Strategies used in while- listening

While- Listening Strategies	Distribution of Unit Theme and Sub-Theme Contents																		F	
	1 A	1 B	1 C	2 A	2 B	2 C	3 A	3 B	3 C	4 A	4 B	4 C	5 A	5 B	5 C	6 A	6 B	6 C		
Note Taking																				
Prediction Studies																				
Envisioning																				
Question Studies	x	x		x	x	x	x		x		x	x		x			x	x	12	
Paying Attention to Emphasis and Intonation																				
Listening Again		x							x									x	3	
Attribution																				
Comparison																		x	1	
Analyzing																				
Repeating																				
Working with Organizational Charts																		x	1	
Setting up an analogy																				
Empathize																				
Working with Words (Keywords, unknown words)									x				x	x				x	4	
Identifying Topic																				
Identifying the main idea																				
Making Markings				x			x		x		x	x						x	x	7
Classification																				
Sorting	x																	x	x	3
Finding Title																				
Producing Solution																				
Summarizing																				
Total (f)	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	4	2	31	

When Table 5 was examined, the following findings were obtained regarding the strategies used in while-listening.

When the while-listening strategies related to the sub-themes of the first unit were examined, strategies for the while-listening were included in each theme. In the last theme of the first unit, only 1 while-listening strategy was used. When the content of the question studies strategy was examined, it was seen that there were true-false and open-ended comprehension types for the content of the listening text.

When the while-listening strategies related to the sub-themes of the second unit were examined, it was seen that each theme included while-listening strategies. The strategies used during listening showed similar characteristics to the first unit. When the content of the question studies strategy was examined, the question types of true-false, matching and filling the gap were included.

When the while-listening strategies related to the sub-themes of the third unit were examined, it was seen that each theme included while-listening strategies. The number of while-listening strategies used in the book's 3D theme was more than the previous unit subthemes. When the content of the "question study" strategies was examined, the types of true-false, matching and sentence completion were included.

When the while-listening strategies related to the sub-themes of the fourth unit were examined, it was seen that each theme included while-listening strategies. The strategies used during listening showed similar features with the previous unit subthemes. When the content of the "question studies" strategy was examined, matching and multiple choice question types were included.

When the while-listening strategies related to the sub-themes of the fifth unit were examined, it was seen that each theme included while-listening strategies. The strategies included show similar features with the previous unit subthemes. Matching question type was used in question studies that were included only once.

When the while-listening strategies for the sub-themes of the sixth unit were examined, it was seen that each theme included while-listening strategies. Working with comparison and organizing tables was used for the first time in the sixth unit sub-themes. Among all themes, the most common while-listening strategy was included in the 6B theme. When the content of the question studies strategy was examined, it was seen that comprehension and matching question type were included.

In all unit subthemes, strategies of while-listening were included. In the content of the while-listening strategies, "question studies" strategies were included in all unit subthemes except for the sixth unit sub-themes. Question studies were seen as the most used strategy among while-listening strategies. The most frequently used question types in the content of question studies strategies were seen as true-false (5 times) and matching (4 times). Following the question studies strategies, the most used strategy was seen as the strategy of making markings. The total use of both strategies was determined to be 19. This figure constituted 61.29% of other strategies used. Although there were 22 while-listening strategies in the classification, more frequent use of two strategies was considered insufficient in terms of quality. Similarly, 15 out of the 22 strategies included in the classification were never used. This situation was considered insufficient quantitatively.

3.3 Listening activities in terms of post-listening strategies

Post-listening activities in the B1 level course book examined within the scope of the study are: "summarizing, evaluating, question studies, making inferences, re-expressing, producing titles, discussion, establishing cause-effect relationships, self-evaluation, questioning, completion studies, working with organizer tables, comparing, giving feedback, criticizing" strategies. However, the strategies used after listening were not tabulated as they were not encountered in any unit sub-theme. It was found out that the information acquired by the learner before and after listening was not integrated, as there were no post-listening activities, which are the steps of evaluation and creation.

The distribution of the listening sections in number throughout the units was seen equally. On the other hand, while-listening activities were included in the sub-themes of all units. Post-listening activities weren't included. There is no systematic approach in ordering the listening activities according to their processes. For example, while pre-listening strategies were included in some units and sub-themes, they were not included in other units and sub-themes.

4. Discussion

Speaking of Turkish in a wide geography from east to west and the large increase in the number of immigrants coming to our country in recent years made it necessary to have a more systematic Turkish education for foreigners. The importance of listening activities included in the content of the course books prepared in this direction has been the subject of various studies in the literature. In this study, the listening activities of the New Istanbul Turkish Teaching course book were examined in terms of listening processes. There is no previous

study on the course book that is the subject of our study. However, there are studies on the previous edition of the book in question, Istanbul Turkish Teaching course book for foreigners and other Turkish teaching course books for foreigners.

The pre-listening activities of the New Istanbul Turkish course book, which is the subject of our research, were examined in terms of procedural strategies within the scope of the determined classification. In the examination, pre-listening strategies were included in only 7 of 18 sub-themes. It was a great deficiency that pre-listening strategies were not included in some units. Although strategies were used in all units during listening, certain strategies were seen to be repeated. Question studies and marking strategies constitute 61.29% of all strategies. Post-listening strategies were not included. The evaluation and synthesis steps were seen as a deficiency in this regard. Gün and Bakırdöğen (2020), Özbal and Genç (2019), Biçer (2019), Yalçın (2018), Gün, Yalçın and Memiş (2017), Tabak and Göçer (2017), Şimşek (2016), Yavuz (2016) and Tuzcu (2011) examined the listening activities of Turkish course books for foreigners in different publications and contents. Similar results were discussed by comparing these studies with our research.

Gün and Bakırdöğen (2020) analyzed Gazi University B1 level listening texts according to the criteria in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages in their study titled "Analysis of Gazi University Level B1 Course book Listening in Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language". There are a total of 5 units in the studied B1 level course book. Four listening activities are included in each unit. A total of 20 listening activities were analyzed in this study. In our study, the content of question studies strategies were seen to be similar to the types of questions in Gazi University course book activities.

Özbal and Genç (2019) in their study titled "Evaluation of Exercises Used in Listening Skills in Course books of Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language," the basic level (A1-A2) course books of the sets "Istanbul Turkish for Foreigners," "Yedi İklim Turkish," "Gazi Turkish for Foreigners" and "New Hitit Turkish for Foreigners" were analyzed in terms of exercises for listening skill. The result is similar to our study that it is necessary to increase the variety of exercises in the listening activities in Istanbul Turkish for Foreigners and Gazi Turkish for Foreigners (A1-A2).

Biçer (2019), in his study titled "Evaluation of Reading and Listening Activities in Course books on Teaching Turkish to Foreigners According to the Revised Bloom Taxonomy," the reading and listening activities of the B1 level course books of the Istanbul, Gazi and Yedi İklim Turkish teaching sets were evaluated in terms of their suitability to recall, comprehension, practice, analyze, evaluate and create classifications. In the evaluation made, it was found out that 26 of the 28 listening activities in the previous edition of the New Istanbul Turkish (B1) book, which is also the subject of our study, were at the comprehension level. In this respect, the result that the activities repeat each other is similar to the repetition of the strategies determined in our research. The results of the absence of post-listening activities in our study and the use of similar strategies during listening activities are consistent with the results of this study.

Yalçın (2018) in his master's thesis titled "Examination of Listening Activities in the Course books of Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language in terms of Language Learning Strategies," reached some conclusions by examining Journey to Turkish Teaching Set C1, Yedi İklim Yunus Emre Institute Turkish Instruction Set C1, Gazi Turkish for Foreigners C1, İzmir Turkish C1 for Foreigners and Istanbul Turkish C1 for Foreigners in terms of Oxford's language learning strategies. The previous edition of the New Istanbul B1 course book, which is the subject of our research, Istanbul B1 course book was examined at C1 level in this study. It is similar to the result of our study, especially in terms of the lack of diversity in language learning strategies.

Gün, Yalçın and Memiş (2017), in their study titled "Comparison of Basic Level Course books Used in Teaching Two Different Languages as a Foreign Language" in terms of Listening Activities, has examined the basic level of Yunus Emre Institute's Turkish Teaching Course book and basic level of New English File course book used in teaching English as a foreign language in terms of listening activities. In the examination, it was found out that there was no pre-listening activity in the basic level course book of the Yunus Emre Institute Turkish Teaching course book. In New Istanbul (B1) level course book examined in our study, pre-listening activities

were included in only 7 sub-themes of 18 sub-themes. In this respect, our study seems to be in close similarity with this study.

Tabak and Göçer (2017) examined 5 A1-C1 level course books published by Gazi TÖMER in terms of procedural listening activities in their research titled "Examination of A1-C1 Level Listening Activities in Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language". As a result of the examinations, it was concluded that the activities were mostly post-listening activities, pre-listening activities were neglected, while-listening activities were not sufficiently included, and similar types of activities were included in the listening processes. This study shows similar features to our study in terms of neglecting pre-listening activities and including similar types of activities in listening processes.

In his master's thesis titled "Comparative analysis of course books used in teaching Turkish to foreigners in the context of basic language skill," Şimşek (2016) examined Yunus Emre Institute Turkish Teaching B2 level course book and Istanbul Turkish Teaching B2 level course book for foreigners comparatively. In the study, four basic language skills were examined on the basis of the determined criteria. Quantitatively, more listening activities were found in the B2 course book of Yunus Emre Institute. While 24 listening activities were included in the Yunus Emre Institute B2 course book, 18 listening activities were included in Istanbul Turkish for foreigners course book. It was concluded that the listening activities included in the Yunus Emre Institute B2 book did not contain pre-listening strategies, and the questions during listening consisted of the same type of questions. In this respect, it can be said that similar results were obtained with our research.

Yavuz (2016) stated that in his master's thesis titled "Listening Activities of Gazi TÖMER Turkish teaching set for foreigners (A1, A2, B1, B2)", the number of activities aimed at improving the listening skill was not sufficient, that pre-listening activities were not sufficiently included, that there were not equal number of activities during and after listening, and that they were not distributed evenly in number, and that students should be able to perceive different aspects of listening by using different types of activities in the procedural listening stages. This study shows similar characteristics to our research. Among the common results of our research, especially the low number of pre-listening activities and not being balanced, and the insufficient listening activities and not benefiting from different activity types can be shown.

Tuzcu (2011), in her master's thesis entitled "Comparison of Basic Level Listening-Comprehension Activities in Teaching Turkish and English as a Foreign Language," examined and evaluated the "New Headway A1-A2" and "New Hitit 1" course books according to the criteria determined based on the Common European Framework. In the evaluation made, it was concluded that listening activities should be organized as before, during and after listening, 'Yeni Hitit 1' course book included basic listening-comprehension activities, but there were mistakes or deficiencies in the organization of the activities, pre-listening activities were not related to the activities during listening, listening activities were similar, post-listening activities were not always included, and listening activities should be diversified. The result expressions for the procedural listening regarding the book "Yeni Hitit 1" are similar to our study.

5. Conclusion

There is no study on the listening activities of the New Istanbul Turkish (B1) level course book and the previous edition of Istanbul Turkish (B1) level course book for foreign students. For this reason, the results were compared in the context of different books and publications discussed in other studies. In the reviewed studies, listening activities were not evaluated on a strategy basis, except for one study. The common deficiencies in the course books examined in terms of results are the low or unbalanced distribution of the number of listening activities, not being associated with other skill areas, insufficient cognitive strategies, not including different activities in procedural listening activities, lacking of language learning strategies, and repetition of activities. It is similar to the results of this study and supports our research. Especially the comparisons made with English teaching books in the literature are important in terms of highlighting these deficiencies.

Attention should be paid to the balanced distribution of procedural strategies in the activities related to listening skills. It should not be forgotten that listening is a process by including strategies before, during and after listening in listening activities in every activity. If post-listening activities are not included, the activities will not go beyond the steps of remembering, understanding, applying and analyzing. This distribution in the contents of the course books should also be taken into account in other skill activities. Different strategies should be used in different listening activities. In addition, this situation should be differentiated according to the student level. It would be particularly useful to combine post-listening activities with a different skill. It is important to use the information acquired before and during listening and transfer it to their own lives. Therefore, post-listening activities should be included and diversity should be provided.

Listening skills can be combined with speaking and writing activities to ensure the integrity of listening activities. Thus, integrity in language learning will be achieved by linking all skills to each other. Since similar situations are detected in other course books examined in the studies, it should be ensured that the activities are strategically enriched and systematically presented in Turkish teaching books for foreigners in terms of quantitative and qualitative aspects.

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